

Evidence Analysis of Tourism and Geographic Location Correlation with Syphilis Incidence

João P. B. Santos, Luiz C. França, Brenda L. Lima, Renato B. Reis, Carolina Spínola and Joberto S. B. Martins

Abstract

Tourism is a valuable source of revenue for countries and communities that contributes to their economic growth. Despite these advantages, tourist travel flow can have unexpected effects, such as spreading diseases, like sexually transmitted infections (STIs), that affect public health. However, identifying possible correlations between tourism activities in regions and disease incidence is a relevant research issue that has not yet been extensively explored. According to the World Health Organization, syphilis is a worldwide STI with an estimated impact of 8 million adults between 15 and 49 years old in 2022. This paper investigates and analyses evidence concerning the correlation between tourism activities and geographical location with syphilis incidence. The correlation analysis uses a machine learning algorithm to cluster the governmental syphilis notification database of Bahia state in Brazil between 2010 and 2019. Evidence analysis suggests correlations between tourism activities in coastal tourism municipalities and the incidence of syphilis. Identified evidence of a correlation allows proactive preventive actions and positively impacts the municipality's public health sector.

Index Terms

Tourism, Syphilis, Machine Learning, Clustering, KMeans, Syphilis Incidence, Tourism Correlation, Syphilis Geographical Correlation

I. INTRODUCTION

Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs) have different etiologies and can be triggered through contact with viruses, bacteria, or other microorganisms, with their transmission occurring predominantly through sexual intercourse without barrier methods. It is a concerning issue, notably in less developed countries where other social determinants may play an essential role in its spread (Teixeira et al., 2022), predominantly affecting vulnerable populations (Assunção et al., 2023).

Travel is widely accepted to be a determining factor in spreading STIs worldwide (Matteelli and Odolini, 2014; Simkhada et al., 2016; Lu et al., 2020; Rogstad, 2019). Memish and Svensson in (Memish and Osoba, 2003; Svensson et al., 2018) add that tourism plays an essential role in this context, notably in coastal regions.

Apart from so-called sex tourists, whose trips are explicitly planned for sexual purposes, usually in countries where prostitution is legal, casual sex between tourists and the host community is also a cause for concern (Lu et al., 2020) due to the change observed in tourist behavior when they are far from their daily lives and in contact with the host communities (Santos & Paiva, 2007; Milhausen et al., 2016; Schäfer, 2020). Research conducted by Vivancos (Vivancos et al., 2010) showed that one out of five travelers has casual sex during a trip, with almost 50% of such sexual encounters being unprotected. Almost the same conclusion was found by Sundbeck (Sundbeck et al., 2016) when studying the risky sexual behavior of young Swedes during their travels and by Lewis (C. T. Lewis and Wildt, 2016) among backpacker tourists visiting Thailand.

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Tourism stands out as one of the most important sectors of the global economy. International tourist arrivals worldwide have been increasing over the years. After recovering from the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, in 2024, 1.4 billion international tourist arrivals were recorded, generating 10.9 trillion dollars in economic activity, equivalent to 10% of the Global Gross Domestic Product. In addition, this sector generated jobs for 357 million people, representing approximately 10.6% of the global workforce (Council, 2025).

Given these outcomes, numerous studies have examined the relationship between the growth of tourism and economic development in the past decades. The findings consistently point to a positive correlation, particularly in areas such as poverty reduction, decreased inequality, and improvements in overall quality of life (Ahmad et al., 2020; Albaladejo et al., 2023; Brida et al., 2016; Brida et al., 2016; Cárdenas-García et al., 2015; Cárdenas-García and Pulido-Fernández, 2019; Min et al., 2016; Yalçinkaya et al., 2018)

However, despite the continuous worldwide growth in visitor flows and positive contribution to the economy of the regions, the possible impacts of tourism with sexual interactions on public health is a research gap in the literature that deals with the interrelationships between tourism and health (Rogstad, 2019).

In this context, this paper addresses the possible impact and correlations existing between tourism and the incidence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), considering syphilis as the case study for the tourism activities in Bahia state in Brazil.

The focus on syphilis is motivated by the fact that each year, it is estimated that 374 million new curable sexually transmitted infections occur, such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea, syphilis, and trichomoniasis. Concerning syphilis, in 2020 alone, 7.1 million adults between 15 and 49 years old would have acquired the disease (WHO, 2023), with more than 60% of new cases occurring in Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) (Peeling et al., 2023). In this context, an in-depth analysis of the data from GeoSentinel travel medicine clinics around the world, syphilis appeared as one of the most common diagnoses among travelers and migrants with STI (Matteelli et al., 2013).

The Bahia state use case comes from the fact that, firstly, in the period between 2011 and 2022, syphilis detection rates had continuous growth, except for pandemic years, reaching the level of 78.5 cases per 100,000 inhabitants at the end of the series (MinistérioDaSaúde, 2022). Concerning tourism, Bahia leads the tourism statistics in northeast Brazil (MinistérioDoTurismo, 2021), as it has the most extensive stretch of coastline in the country, bringing together many of the main beach destinations, making it more susceptible to the incidence of STIs involving tourists. Furthermore, in Brazil, the compulsory notification of acquired syphilis was established in 2010, providing a reliable public database for 10 years.

The paper's main contribution to tourism and health areas is to identify the correlations between tourism flow and the incidence of syphilis in distinct geographic locations. An additional academic contribution concerns the use of machine learning to identify these correlations. Machine learning algorithms present advantages for inference analysis and predictive model development (Xu, Ge, et al., 2022). The ML-based approach is data-driven, identifies complex patterns, and exploits complex dataset interactions. Disease risk prediction and incident analysis using health and social data have recently shown a potential application area for ML methods (Uddin et al., 2019; Queiroz and Martins, 2024).

The results of our ML-based analysis of the correlation between tourism and syphilis suggest that coastal cities are more susceptible to syphilis incidence.

This paper is organized as follows. Section I contextualizes the target scenario, indicating main contributions and the research outcomes. Section II presents the related work. Section III introduces the clustering background, followed by Section V presenting the syphilis incidence dataset and experiment setup. The section VI presents the clustering experiment run, and section VII analyses the evidence of tourism and geographical location impact on syphilis incidence. Finally, Section VIII presents the final considerations.

II. RELATED WORK

Despite the growth in tourism flows around the world, the impacts of sexual interactions on the spread of syphilis cases in host communities is still a subject that has been little studied in the literature. The

review carried out in this article found two main groups of works on the topic.

The first one covers studies that address the factors that influence the risky sexual behavior of tourists in general (M. A. Lewis et al., 2014; Svensson et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2020), in specific segments such as young people (Sundbeck et al., 2016; Gareau and Phillips, 2022), backpackers (C. T. Lewis and Wildt, 2016), men who have sex with men (Person et al., 2018; Mao et al., 2018), tourists who have intimate relationships with workers in the sector (Simkhada et al., 2016) and sex workers (Quaife et al., 2023; Bozicevic et al., 2020) and, finally, papers seeking to understand the existing barriers to the use of condoms (Milhausen et al., 2016; Lejelind et al., 2017; S. Bishop and Limmer, 2018). This group of works differs from ours in the fact that it focuses on looking for risky sexual behavior in specific segments influencing syphilis incidence. In contrast, our approach focuses on the location or event-based syphilis incidence for all human groups.

The second group gathers research that relates travel and tourism to the occurrence of STIs among tourists upon returning to their countries of origin (Memish and Osoba, 2003; Vivancos et al., 2010; Matteelli et al., 2013; Rogstad, 2019) and with a particular interest in HIV (Herold and Van Kerkwijk, 1992; Hawkes and Hart, 1993; Johnson, 2016; Brett-Major et al., 2016; Pérez-Molina et al., 2016; Soriano and Romero, 2018; Bourque et al., 2019; Nouchi et al., 2019; Du et al., 2022), but also about Gonorrhea (Beauté et al., 2017) and Chlamydia trachomatis (Aung et al., 2019). This second group of papers, in summary, focuses on the occurrence of the generic occurrence of STIs in tourists upon returning to their countries. In contrast, our approach focuses on the incidence of a specific STI (syphilis) in local communities. The local focus is pivotal for proactive municipal health planning and responsive and ready management.

Among the research papers addressing syphilis, specifically, studies have been found that associate it with HIV-positive tourists (Salavec et al., 2014; Matteelli and Odolini, 2014). At the other extreme, this time addressing sex workers, Nzivo et al. (Nzivo et al., 2019) surveyed the prevalence and risk factors for syphilis and herpes virus among prostitutes in Malindi, a region of Kenya whose economy is heavily dependent on tourism and which attracts visitors from different parts of the world.

As for risk groups for syphilis contamination and dissemination, Loosier et al. (Loosier et al., 2021) conducted ethnographic research in Anchorage, Alaska, to identify factors related to the sudden increase in notifications among men who have sex with men and found aspects related to the practices of these patients during their travels. Schafer (Schäfer, 2020) highlights the increase in cases of syphilis and attributes this to a mismatch between the information available on the risks associated with unprotected sex with strangers and the level of concern of visitors regarding this issue.

In Brazil, recent production is more associated with gestational and congenital syphilis, both in terms of its diagnosis and treatment (Cabral et al., 2017; Figueiredo et al., 2020) and the spatial distribution of notifications in the country (Signor et al., 2018) and in the states of Espírito Santo (Soares et al., 2020) and Rio Grande do Norte (Raimundo et al., 2021).

Acquired syphilis is addressed by Assunção work (Assunção et al., 2023), which analyzes the socio-economic profile of patients affected by the disease in the state of Rio Grande do Norte, confirming what is stated in the literature, with a more significant predominance of groups with low education, mixed race, and young adults.

Regarding the relationship between the disease and tourism, Helbusto (Helbusto et al., 2016), in an ecological epidemiological study that analyzed health indicators in coastal tourist cities in Brazil, found a higher incidence of congenital syphilis and hepatitis B compared to general data. This work is close to our research by looking at the relations between tourism and syphilis. However, it differs in the fact that it considers health indicators in general for congenital syphilis and hepatitis B.

Except for one, all the works analyzed were published in health journals, with significant research participation in nursing. No articles were published in tourism journals, demonstrating the need for more interdisciplinary discussions that support public health policies associated with the sector's dynamics. Complementarily, most of the analyzed articles focused on the tourists themselves, considering them vulnerable when traveling to regions classified as at risk, with little attention given to host communities

and the need to develop actions to reduce their morbidity rates.

Concerning the chosen artificial intelligence methodology, Teixeira (Teixeira et al., 2022) evaluates some machine learning models for predicting the incidence of congenital syphilis to optimize healthcare actions. Syphilis prediction is addressed by Aral et al. in (Young et al., 2018) using social network data. Sexually transmitted infections (STI) risk prediction is presented in Xu et al. in (Xu, Yu, et al., 2022) and an additional approach for HIV/STI using a set of machine learning-based algorithms for disease analysis is proposed by Xu et al. in (Xu, Ge, et al., 2022). In contrast to the mentioned methodologies, our AI clustering method seeks to identify geographic interrelations and local aspects of syphilis incidence.

To the best of our knowledge, the correlation between syphilis incidence and tourism flow and geographical locations of municipalities in a delimited and interconnected area is a new approach addressed by this paper.

III. THE CLUSTERING METHOD FOR THE SYPHILIS INCIDENCE CORRELATION ANALYSIS

The machine learning method used to analyze the evidence of tourism’s impact on syphilis incidence is clustering (Jain, 2010). In the context of the Bahia state analysis, the clustering method aggregates distributed syphilis incidence spatially by municipality and geographical region.

Clustering algorithms employ various approaches to cluster data, and, as such, the best-fit algorithm depends on specific criteria, including the dataset’s characteristics and research objectives (Shtern and Tzerpos, 2009). In this research analysis of tourism and geographic location impact on syphilis incidence, the KMeans algorithm (Ester et al., 1996) was used due to the following aspects:

- KMeans assumes that clusters are spherical, with similar size and variance, which leads to grouping syphilis incidence occurrences into similar group categories;
- KMeans allows the control of the number of clusters, that allows an interactive refining of the clustering according to the research problem objectives; and
- It can scale to large datasets and is relatively easy to use.

In summary, KMeans is an adequate approach that allows a syphilis incidence database to be refined for segmentation.

A. Clustering Methods Background

There are two basic classes of clustering algorithms: i) Center-based clusters; and ii) High-density clusters. Center-based clusters assume that the clustering can be defined by k center points c_1, \dots, c_k , with each data point assigned to whichever center point is closest to it. The k -center clustering approach finds a partition $C = C_1, \dots, C_k$ of the set of points A into k clusters, with corresponding centers c_1, \dots, c_k , that minimizes the maximum distance between any data point and the center of its cluster. The k -median clustering finds a partition that minimizes the sum of distances between data points and the centers of their clusters. Examples of center-based algorithms are KMeans (Forgy, 1965), Gaussian Mixture Models (C. M. Bishop, 2006), and K-Medoids.

High-density clustering is an alternative to center-based clustering in which clusters consist of high-density regions surrounded by low-density regions between them. DBScan (Ester et al., 1996), OPTICS, and MeanShift are examples of high-density clustering algorithms.

Our research considers two main clustering options: KMeans (Forgy, 1965) and DBscan (Ester et al., 1996). The proposed KMeans clustering method adequately addresses specific challenges and issues related to disease incidence in a geographical area. KMeans offers specific advantages concerning the research goals, such as being more computationally efficient than DBScan and better performing over uniformly distributed data. KMeans being more efficient computationally is always an advantage, even when a large dataset is not computed. In addition, syphilis incidence is spread relatively evenly over spaces like municipalities that were the focus of the incident reports collected by the healthcare government institutions in Bahia state. Another complementary aspect is that KMeans is less sensitive to parameter tuning than DBSCAN, and the experiment dataset has few outliers.

The KMeans clustering algorithm, in summary, partitions data into k clusters by assigning each data point to the cluster with the nearest centroid. Centroids are recalculated iteratively to minimize data point distances to the centers.

KMeans clustering uses various methods to evaluate clustering quality, like the Silhouette score (Zhao et al., 2018), the Calinski-Harabasz index (Guo et al., 2017), and the Davies-Bouldin index (Davies and Bouldin, 1979).

The silhouette score is the main metric used to evaluate the clustering quality in this research. Generally, a high average silhouette score indicates that the clustering is well-separated and that the observations within each cluster are similar. A low score indicates that the clustering is not well-separated and that the observations within each cluster are not very similar. The silhouette score is a tailored evaluation metric used to evaluate KMeans.

IV. SPATIAL ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

The syphilis evidence analysis design is ecological to establish an association between possible risk factors and the occurrence of the event (syphilis incidence), measured by population groups, geographic area, and time interval (Medronho et al., 2009). The methodology uses secondary data from the Notifiable Diseases Information System (SINAN) made available by the Ministry of Health.

The study covered notifications related to the location of syphilis incidence, with the state of Bahia as the focus. Bahia is located in the northeastern region of Brazil and consists of 417 municipalities. It occupies the equivalent of 6.63% of the national territory and has an estimated population of 14,141,626 inhabitants, which represents 6.65% of the national population.

The incidence rates of syphilis were georeferenced for spatial analysis. This resource associates data or information with a geographic position in space through coordinates or the unit of analysis (municipality). The spatial distribution of the incidence rates is performed using QGIS3.34 software.

A. Spatial Autocorrelation

Exploratory spatial data analysis (ESDA) helps show possible correlations between a given variable in space. This type of analysis deals with the effects resulting from dependence and spatial heterogeneity (Almeida, 2012).

Spatial correlation occurs when the value of a variable in region i is related to the value of the same variable in region j . ESDA is useful for describing and visualizing spatial distributions and identifying possible clusters or association patterns. The degree of neighborhood that one wants to consider in the analysis through a weight matrix. In this study, different weight matrices were tested with different neighborhood criteria, including different higher orders, to identify the one that presented the highest and most significant value of Moran's I statistic.

Global indicators of spatial autocorrelation, such as the one presented above, provide a single value as a measure of spatial association. However, when a large number of areas are considered, local maxima of spatial autocorrelation may emerge.

The LISA (Local Indicator of Spatial Association) analysis methodology is the statistical measure used in spatial analysis in this dataset to identify localized areas where data values exhibit significant spatial clustering. This analysis fundamentally examines spatial autocorrelation at the local level.

In this case, the dependence between regions tends to be stronger, making it necessary to analyze spatial patterns in more detail. This is done through local indicators, which produce a specific value for each area. This strategy allows for the identification of clusters and outliers and the presence of more than one spatial regime. The local indicator of spatial association can be formally presented as:

$$I_i = \frac{z_i \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} z_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

where:

- I_i is the local Moran index for the unit i .
- z_i is the variable of interest standardized to unity i .
- w_{ij} is the element of the spatial weight matrix between units i and j .
- n is the number of units in the study.

The Torre matrix was used in this study, as it presented the largest and most significant Moran's I. As before, Z is the value of the standardized variable of interest. The Moran I statistic was calculated for the incidence of syphilis cases in Bahia municipalities. The analysis was performed using GEODA software version 1.12.1.131.

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate Moran I evaluation and the local indicator of spatial association (LISA) of syphilis incidence for the state of Bahia, indicating the effectiveness of the dataset.

Figure 1. Moran I Evaluation

Figure 2. Scatter diagram of Global Moran Index I

V. DATASET AND SYPHILIS INCIDENCE CLUSTERING SETUP

The syphilis incidence dataset used and the syphilis clustering setup are described in this section.

A. Dataset

The acquired dataset used in the KMeans clustering experiment concerns all types of syphilis, with notifications collected by Bahia's State Health Secretary (Brazil) from 2010 to 2023. The pandemic period was excluded from Bahia's database to avoid evaluating during a period with anomalous and restricted tourist behavior, since the impact of tourist mobility is the main focus.

The clustering experiment run uses notifications from 2010 to 2019. The syphilis incidence notification dataset is available at Martins et al. (Martins et al., 2024) and includes the following information:

- Municipalities of Bahia (municipality code and population) (417 municipalities);
- Number of cases of syphilis per municipality cumulative from 2010 to 2019; and
- Municipality's tourism categorization.

The municipality's tourism categorization is based on a categorization defined by the Ministry of Tourism of Brazil (MinistérioDoTurismo, 2024). In summary, the municipality categorization is as follows:

- Municipality type "A": Municipalities with complete tourist infrastructure, a wide variety of attractions, high tourist flow, and efficient management. It corresponds to a highly touristic municipality;
- Municipality type "B": Municipalities with good infrastructure, diversified tourist attractions, moderate tourist flow, and developing management;
- Municipality type "C": Municipalities with basic infrastructure and tourist attractions are present but have potential for development, and the tourist flow is still growing;
- Municipality type "D": Municipalities with limited infrastructure, incipient tourist attractions, and low tourist flow;
- Municipality type "E": Municipalities with less tourist potential, generally with few attractions and precarious infrastructure; and
- Municipality type "F" - a municipality with no tourist flow or capabilities.

The syphilis incidence notification dataset structure is detailed in Appendix A and illustrated in Figure 3 (Martins et al., 2024).

Municipality Code	Municipality Name	Syphilis Cases	Inhabitants	Tourism Category
...
291220	Ibicoara	15	19786	2
291230	Ibiciuí	17	16796	0
291240	Ibipeba	4	18678	0
...
...

Figure 3. Syphilis Incidence Notification Dataset Sample in Bahia State - Brazil (2010 - 2019).

The first step of the clustering process with KMeans is to process the syphilis incidence notification dataset to normalize the incidence data by municipality. The normalization was done considering the cumulative quantity of incidence cases by a municipality in the 10-year notification period rated against the actual municipality population. This normalized parameter differs from the classical rating of incidence cases by population group (100,000 inhabitants) but fits the required target in clustering, which is to compare and group similar municipalities in terms of syphilis incidence rate. In effect, the normalized incidence indicated the intensity of syphilis incidence as a percentage of the population over 10 years. Our target is not to compare incidence numbers but to cluster similar incidence groups.

Binary encoding was further used for the category variables representing the six tourism category classifications ("A" to "F") for all municipalities as illustrated in (Table I).

During the dataset pre-processing, variables such as tourism category, municipality code, and population size were either excluded or converted to align with the KMeans clustering algorithm and analysis objectives.

Table I
NORMALIZED AND BINARY ENCODED SYPHILIS DATABASE SAMPLE

Municipality Order	Incidence	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
1	7	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	5	0	0	0	0	0	1
3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
4	9	0	0	0	1	0	1
...

B. Syphilis Incidence Clustering and PyCaret Framework

The experiment was configured on a Windows Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-3470 CPU @ 3.20GHz desktop. Some machine learning analysis scripts were executed using Visual Studio Code v.1.73.0 and Python v3.10.6. PyCaret 3.0 (Ali, 2020) is the framework used to run the syphilis incidence clustering experiment.

The machine learning algorithm (KMeans) configuration parameters, the KMeans simulation run parameters, and simulation results (processed database, figures, charts, other) are available at <https://github.com/joberto/PyCaretDatasetPPDRU>.

VI. SYPHILIS INCIDENCE CLUSTERING RESULTS

The KMeans model was trained multiple times in PyCaret to refine the data distribution and minimize the presence of outliers, which could distort the results. Repeating and optimizing the algorithm increased the clustering accuracy and resulted in a more precise segmentation of the municipalities based on the syphilis incidence rates. The accuracy of the clustering is analyzed through the algorithm's output, specifically the Silhouette score, which indicates how well-defined the clusters are. After the training and clustering run, a labeling function was applied to the defined clusters, allowing the processed data to be visualized and analyzed more efficiently.

Figure 4 illustrates the four clusters (Cluster 0 to 3) resulting from Bahia municipality's syphilis incidence database, and Table II shows the parameters associated with each cluster.

Figure 4. Municipalities Clustering for Bahia State - Brazil.

Table II
CLUSTERS AND SYPHILIS INCIDENCE RANGE AND NUMBER OF MUNICIPALITIES

Cluster	Syphilis Incidence Range	Number of Municipalities
Cluster 0	0 - 0,089	257
Cluster 1	0,09 - 0,179	87
Cluster 2	0,182 - 0,350	50
Cluster 3	0,355 - 1,06	23

The clusters have the following characteristics:

- Cluster 0 and 1: Are considered low incidence clusters, grouping 344 municipalities with normalized incidence ranging from 0 to 0,179; and
- Cluster 2 and 3: Are considered high incidence clusters, grouping 73 municipalities having normalized incidence ranging from 0,182 to 1,06.

Table III presents the clustering efficiency metrics using KMeans for the syphilis incidence data across municipalities in Bahia. The metrics include the Silhouette score, Calinski-Harabasz index, and Davies-Bouldin score, which together evaluate the quality of the clustering algorithm used.

Table III
KMEANS CLUSTERING EFFICIENCY METRICS

Silhouette	Calinski-Harabasz	Davies-Bouldin
0,67	350,37	0,54

The average Silhouette score of 0,67 (above 0,5) suggests suitable clustering. This result is the highest average silhouette score following the interactive process defining the number of clusters, indicating the best possible clustering quality.

The obtained Calinski-Harabasz score of 350,37 is relatively high and suggests that the clustering is well-defined. The score signifies a good separation between the clusters (high inter-cluster variance) relative to their tightness (low intra-cluster variance), meaning the clusters are distinct and compact.

Finally, having a Davies-Bouldin index of 0,54 also indicates that the clustering solution is reasonably good, with clusters that are relatively well-separated and internally compact.

1) *Experiment Post-Processing:* In the post-processing phase of the experiment, the syphilis cases and clustered data were processed using the Pandas library to create a view of the syphilis case distribution in Bahia state with the following main indicators:

- Municipalities and syphilis incidence;
- Syphilis cases by tourist category; and
- Coastal and non-coastal municipalities syphilis incidence.

Clustering is an exploratory analysis technique. The experiment results are first evaluated as having the best possible clustering result and then interpreted in the context of the syphilis incidence scenario. These pre-processing methods allow us to understand the characteristics of the clusters and relate the incidence of syphilis to population, tourism, and other geographic factors.

VII. EVIDENCE ANALYSIS OF MUNICIPALITY TOURISM CATEGORY AND GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION CORRELATION WITH SYPHILIS INCIDENCE

The KMeans clustering of the syphilis incidence dataset resulted in four clusters with syphilis incidence parameters illustrated in Table II. For this paper analysis, clusters 2 and 3 are considered the most relevant ones with a high incidence of syphilis. Cluster 3 encompasses 23 cities with 20,782 cases, while Cluster 2 comprises 50 cities with 4,370 cases.

On the other hand, the classification of municipalities by tourism category is illustrated in Table IV and Figure 5. For this paper's analysis, we consider categories 4 and 5 as the most relevant tourism locations, based on the Ministry of Tourism's classification criteria, which indicate high tourism flow and economic impact.

The evidence analysis of the impact of tourism and geographical location on syphilis incidence is first evaluated by cross-referencing the clustering grouping with the spatial distribution of the disease, using indicators such as tourism categories and geographical spaces. In summary, the analysis of clustering data is done considering the following aspects:

- Syphilis incidence for all municipalities;
- Syphilis incidence by the municipality tourism category; and

Table IV
TOURISM CATEGORY AND NUMBER OF MUNICIPALITIES IN BAHIA STATE

Tourism Category	Number of Municipalities
Category 0	284
Category 1	12
Category 2	64
Category 3	31
Category 4	21
Category 5	5

Figure 5. Municipalities Tourism Categorization in Bahia State (category 0 to 5)

- Syphilis incidence by municipality location: coastal and non-coastal.

The geographical distribution of syphilis incidence in Bahia's municipalities based on clustering is illustrated in Figure 6. Clusters 2 and 3 group municipalities with high syphilis incidence ranging from 0,182 to 1,06 (Table II), which, from the perspective of this paper, are the focal point of the correlation analysis between syphilis incidence and tourism geographical location. A simple and informal visual inspection reveals that many municipalities in these clusters are located near the coastline, suggesting a possible correlation that warrants further evaluation.

As a second analytical perspective, the geographical distribution of high-tourism municipalities (categories 4 and 5), as defined by the Brazilian Ministry of Tourism, is illustrated in Figure 7. Again, most high-tourism municipalities are distributed along the coastline.

Figure 8 superposes the municipalities with high syphilis incidence (clusters 2 and 3) with the municipalities categorized by the Ministry of Tourism as having high tourism economic impact (categories 4 and 5). The superposition suggests that there is no strong correlation between these categories. In effect, only a few high tourism municipalities have high syphilis incidence numbers. Table V shows the number of municipalities with a high tourism category for clusters 2 and 3 that have high syphilis incidence. In summary, it validates the former analysis since only 8% and 30,5% of municipalities with category 4 and 5 have high syphilis incidence in clusters 2 and 3, respectively.

Figure 6. Geographical Distribution of Syphilis Incidence in Bahia's Municipalities Based on Clustering

Table V
CLUSTERS WITH SYPHILIS INCIDENCE AND HIGH TOURISM MUNICIPALITIES

Cluster	Municipality - Category 4 and 5	Total Number of Municipalities per Cluster
Cluster 2	4	50
Cluster 3	7	23

The correlation mismatch between municipalities with high syphilis incidence and high tourism can be, at least in part, explained by a deeper analysis of local aspects. In effect, the Ministry of Tourism criteria to classify a municipality as one having a significant tourism impact considers other aspects beyond the number of tourist flow, and the number of tourists is one of the most relevant parameters that will induce contact and sexually transmitted infections in our analysis.

In effect, tourism categories are defined by the Ministry of Tourism based on the formal tourism supply and support structure and the size of the visitor flows that a municipality receives. As such, despite having a high tourist flow, municipalities characterized by the great informality of their economies are excluded from this classification. In addition, essential parameters such as motivation, length of stay, and demographic profile of tourists are not considered. Consequently, there are municipalities classified as 4 or 5 on the Tourism Map that, in reality, are medium-sized cities with significant commercial and service importance, as is the case of Alagoinhas, Juazeiro, Paulo, Afonso, Jequié, and Vitória da Conquista in Bahia state. Likewise, municipalities whose predominant flow seeks motivations such as religious or nature tourism 'escape' from this group, which would be the case of Bom Jesus da Lapa and Lençóis, still in Bahia state. In coastal tourist municipalities, it is worth highlighting those that position themselves as second-home destinations with a more family-friendly profile, like Vera Cruz, Itaparica, Valença, and Camaçari.

These limiting aspects concerning the Ministry of Tourism's categorization of municipalities as having significant tourism activities suggest that other correlation approaches, like syphilis incidence in coastal municipalities, could be investigated. In addition, we suggest new alternatives for municipalities' tourism classification, like length of stay, tourist demographic profile of tourists, real-time tourist mobility data,

Figure 7. High Tourism Municipalities - Categories 4 and 5

mobile tracking, or hotel/occupancy statistics, to improve classification relevance.

Concerning coastal line municipalities' correlation with syphilis incidence, Figure 9 illustrates the superposition of coastline municipalities with municipalities having high syphilis incidence (clusters 2 and 3). Analysis of syphilis incidence in Bahia State 417 municipalities, with 46 coastal municipalities, reveals a significant pattern in the distribution of syphilis cases along the coastline.

A higher prevalence of syphilis is identified in coastal cities, especially noticeable in Cluster 3, where 72.67% of cases are concentrated in coastal areas (Table VI). These data suggest that coastal cities are more susceptible to disease incidence, with economic and social attractions that promote increased population movement, including temporary residents and tourists. In Cluster 2, coastal cities account for 42.49% of cases, considering coastal cities represent less than half of the cities allocated in this cluster. In contrast, this influence decreases significantly in Clusters 1 and 0, indicating less dependence on the coastal factor for the incidence of cases.

Table VI
COASTLINE MUNICIPALITIES WITH HIGH SYPHILIS INCIDENCE (CLUSTERS 2 AND 3)

Cluster	Coastal Municipality with High Incidence	Municipalities at Coast Line	Rate
Cluster 2	4	14	42,5%
Cluster 3	7	5	72%

These numbers suggest that a combination of coastal location with tourist characteristics, not considered in the categorization used by the Ministry of Tourism, can lead to a higher incidence of syphilis. In Cluster 3, this combination results in a high number of cases, demonstrating how these factors, when present simultaneously, can create an environment conducive to the incidence of syphilis. The recurrence of cases in coastal cities with tourist characteristics in this cluster contrasts with other clusters, where the influence of one factor alone is less pronounced.

Figure 8. High Tourism Municipalities (tourism categories 4 and 5) with High Syphilis Incidence (clusters 2 and 3)

VIII. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Tourism is increasing worldwide and benefits countries and cities by creating jobs, increasing company revenue, and improving government tax collection. As such, higher tourism activities are an unstoppable trend followed by countries and municipalities stimulating this activity. However, unexpected impacts of tourism, like the spread of STI diseases, must be observed by identifying possible correlations between tourism activity and the spread of STI diseases in relation to diverse aspects of the municipalities.

This paper investigated possible correlations between syphilis incidence and municipalities' tourism activities and geographic location characteristics. The evidence analysis indicates a high prevalence of syphilis in coastal cities that have significant tourism activities and tourist flow. Our analysis suggests that coastal cities are more susceptible to disease incidence, with economic and social attractions promoting increased population movement, including temporary residents and tourists.

The evidence analysis demonstrating that tourism in coastal locations correlates with syphilis incidence provides a basis for creating municipalities' public health policies, focused urban planning, and promoting educational measures to reduce or mitigate the incidence of syphilis in these potential risk areas worldwide.

The evidence analysis concerning the occurrence of syphilis based on tourism flow has some limitations. Confounding variables impacting syphilis spread and incidence include aspects not considered in the collected information, such as socioeconomic status, healthcare access, public health policies, population density, education level, and others discussed in the literature, such as sexual behavior, sexual orientation, and alcohol and drug use. These aspects are outside our current scope. In future work, we plan to extend the analysis to consider, among others, the target population's educational level, which reflects its level of conscientiousness and serves as a parameter for estimating and analyzing the impact of public syphilis educational campaigns promoted in potentially affected municipalities.

Another limitation concerns the actual government tourism categorization, which presents some bias concerning municipalities' political aspects and requires more in-depth technical precision. This limitation will be addressed as a non-technical but politically convincing work, together with Bahia's government, towards improving government methods to collect tourism data on municipalities that prioritize the

Figure 9. Bahia State - Coastal Municipalities with High Syphilis Incidence

technical aspects of the problem. As a future scientific work, we consider the possibility of externalizing the limitations' findings of this work by proposing a worldwide tourism classification method focused on disease propagation identification requirements and its contour variables.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, N., Menegaki, A. N., & Al-Muharrami, S. (2020). Systematic Literature Review of Tourism Growth Nexus: An Overview of the Literature and a Content Analysis of 100 Most Influential Papers. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 34(5), 1068–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12386>
- Albaladejo, I. P., Brida, J. G., González-Martínez, M. I., & Segarra, V. (2023). A New Look to the Tourism and Economic Growth Nexus: A Clustering and Panel Causality Analysis. *The World Economy*, 46(9), 2835–2856. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.13459>
- Ali, M. (2020, April). *Pycaret: An open source, low-code machine learning library in python* [PyCaret version 1.0]. <https://www.pycaret.org>
- Almeida, E. (2012). *Econometria Espacial Aplicada*. ALINEA.
- Assunção, T. B. O., Veras, N. V. R., Neto, C. L. d. B. G., Guerra, Â. R. O., Silva, R. P. d., Oliveira, F. A. d. S., Sodr, C. J., Souza, W. W. V., & Silva, A. L. M. d. (2023). Anlise Situacional da Sfilis entre os Anos de 2015 e 2021 no Estado do Rio Grande do Norte. *Brazilian Journal of Sexually Transmitted Diseases*, 35.
- Aung, E. T., Chow, E. P., Fairley, C. K., Hocking, J. S., Bradshaw, C. S., Williamson, D. A., & Chen, M. Y. (2019). International Travel as Risk Factor for Chlamydia Trachomatis Infections Among Young Heterosexuals Attending a Sexual Health Clinic in Melbourne, Australia, 2007 to 2017. *Euro Surveillance*, 24(44), 1900219.
- Beaut, J., Cowan, S., Hiltunen-Back, E., Klvstad, H., Velicko, I., & Spiteri, G. (2017). Travel-Associated Gonorrhoea in Four Nordic Countries, 2008 to 2013. *Euro Surveillance*, 22(20), 30537.
- Bishop, C. M. (2006). *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

- Bishop, S., & Limmer, M. (2018). Performance, Power and Condom Use: Reconceptualised Masculinities Amongst Western Male Sex Tourists to Thailand. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 20(3), 276–288.
- Bourque, D. L., Solomon, D. A., & Sax, P. E. (2019). Health Considerations for HIV-Infected International Travelers. *Current Infectious Disease Reports*, 21(5), 16.
- Bozicevic, I., Manathunge, A., Beneragama, S., & Gadjaweera, C. (2020). Beach Boys in Galle, Sri Lanka: Multiple HIV Risk Behaviours and Potential for HIV Bridging. *BMC public health*, 20(1), 1604.
- Brett-Major, D. M., Scott, P. T., Crowell, T. A., Polyak, C. S., Modjarrad, K., Robb, M. L., & Blazes, D. L. (2016). Are you PEPPed and PrEPped for travel? Risk mitigation of HIV infection for travelers. *Tropical Diseases, Travel Medicine and Vaccines*, 2, 25.
- Brida, J. G., Isabel, C.-J., & Pulina, M. (2016). Has the Tourism-Led Growth Hypothesis Been Validated? A Literature Review. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 19(5), 394–430. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2013.868414>
- Cabral, B. T. V., Dantas, J. d. C., Silva, J. A. d., & Oliveira, D. A. d. (2017). Sífilis em Gestante e Sífilis Congênita: Um Estudo Retrospectivo. *Rev. Ciênc. Plur*, 32–44.
- Cárdenas-García, P. J., & Pulido-Fernández, J. I. (2019). Tourism as an Economic Development Tool. Key Factors. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 22(17), 2082–2108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2017.1420042>
- Cárdenas-García, P. J., Sánchez-Rivero, M., & Pulido-Fernández, J. I. (2015). Does Tourism Growth Influence Economic Development? *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(2), 206–221. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287513514297>
- Council, W. T. a. T. (2025). Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2024: Global Trends. Retrieved June 10, 2025, from <https://wttc.org/research/economic-impact>
- Davies, D. L., & Bouldin, D. W. (1979). A Cluster Separation Measure. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, PAMI-1(2), 224–227.
- Du, M., Yuan, J., Jing, W., Liu, M., & Liu, J. (2022). The Effect of International Travel Arrivals on the New HIV Infections in 15-49 Years Aged Group Among 109 Countries or Territories From 2000 to 2018. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 833551.
- Ester, M., Kriegel, H.-P., Sander, J., & Xu, X. (1996). A Density-Based Algorithm for Discovering Clusters in Large Spatial Databases with Noise. *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 226–231.
- Figueiredo, D. C. M. M. d., Figueiredo, A. M. d., Souza, T. K. B. d., Tavares, G., & Vianna, R. P. d. T. (2020). Relação entre Oferta de Diagnóstico e Tratamento da Sífilis na Atenção Básica sobre a Incidência de Sífilis Gestacional e Congênita [Publisher: Escola Nacional de Saúde Pública Sergio Arouca, Fundação Oswaldo Cruz]. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, 36, e00074519.
- Forgy, E. W. (1965). Cluster Analysis of Multivariate Data: Efficiency Versus Interpretability of Classifications. *Biometrics*.
- Gareau, E., & Phillips, K. P. (2022). Sexual Behaviors at Home and Abroad: An Online Survey of Canadian Young Adult Travelers. *BMC public health*, 22(1), 967.
- Guo, G., Chen, L., Ye, Y., & Jiang, Q. (2017). Cluster Validation Method for Determining the Number of Clusters in Categorical Sequences. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 28(12), 2936–2948.
- Hawkes, S. J., & Hart, G. J. (1993). Travel, Migration and HIV. *AIDS care*, 5(2), 207–214.
- Helbusto, N. B., Calheiros, C. F., Souza, L. d. A. A., & Vianna, P. V. C. (2016). Cidades Turísticas Litorâneas: A Economia Vai Bem, mas e a Saúde? *Revista Univap*, 22(40), 425–425.
- Herold, E., & Van Kerkwijk, C. (1992). Aids and Sex Tourism. *AIDS & society*, 4(1).
- Jain, A. K. (2010). Data Clustering: 50 Years Beyond K-Means. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 31(8), 651–666.
- Johnson, L. C. (2016). 'Men at Risk': Sex Work, Tourism, and STI/HIV Risk in Jamaica. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 18(9), 1025–1038.

- Lejelind, E., Westerling, R., Sjögren Fugl-Meyer, K., & Larsson, K. (2017). Condom Use Among Swedes While Traveling Internationally: A Qualitative Descriptive Study. *Nursing & Health Sciences*, *19*(2), 257–263.
- Lewis, C. T., & Wildt, G. d. (2016). Sexual Behaviour of Backpackers Who Visit Koh Tao and Koh Phangan, Thailand: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Sexually Transmitted Infections*, *92*(6), 410–414.
- Lewis, M. A., Patrick, M. E., Mittmann, A., & Kaysen, D. L. (2014). Sex on the Beach: The Influence of Social Norms and Trip Companion on Spring Break Sexual Behavior. *Prevention Science*, *15*(3), 408–418.
- Loosier, P. S., Carry, M., Fasula, A., Hatfield-Timajchy, K., Jones, S. A., Harvill, J., Smith, T., & McLaughlin, J. (2021). An Investigation of Early Syphilis Among Men Who have Sex with Men: Alaska, 2018: Findings from a 2018 Rapid Ethnographic Assessment. *Journal of Community Health*, *46*(1), 22–30.
- Lu, T. S., Holmes, A., Noone, C., & Flaherty, G. T. (2020). Sun, Sea and Sex: A Review of the Sex Tourism Literature. *Tropical Diseases, Travel Medicine and Vaccines*, *6*(1), 24.
- Mao, J., Tang, W., Liu, C., Wong, N. S., Tang, S., Wei, C., & Tucker, J. D. (2018). Sex Tourism Among Chinese Men Who Have Sex with Men: A Cross-Sectional Observational Study. *BMC public health*, *18*(1), 306.
- Martins, J., Santos, J., França, L., Reis, R., Lima, B., & Spínola, C. (2024). *Syphilis and tourism and geographic location dataset - syphogl*. <https://doi.org/10.21227/0y08-y911>
- Matteelli, A., & Odolini, S. (2014). Travel, syphilis and HIV. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, *12*(1), 5–6.
- Matteelli, A., Schlagenhauf, P., Carvalho, A. C., Weld, L., Davis, X. M., Wilder-Smith, A., Barnett, E. D., Parola, P., Pandey, P., Han, P., Castelli, F., & GeoSentinel Surveillance Network. (2013). Travel-Associated Sexually Transmitted Infections: An Observational Cross-Sectional Study of the Geosentinel Surveillance Database. *The Lancet. Infectious Diseases*, *13*(3), 205–213.
- Medronho, R. A., Bloch, K. V., Luiz, R. R., & Werneck, G. L. (2009). *Epidemiologia*. Atheneu.
- Memish, Z. A., & Osoba, A. O. (2003). Sexually Transmitted Diseases and Travel. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*, *21*(2), 131–134.
- Milhausen, R. R., Crosby, R. A., Yarber, W. L., Graham, C. A., Sanders, S. A., Ingram, H., Barr, V. M., & Macdonald, I. R. (2016). An Intervention Study Assessing a Peer Outreach Model to Promote Safer-Sex for Tourism Workers. *The Canadian Journal of Human Sexuality*, *25*(3), 216–224.
- Min, C.-k., Taek-seon, R., & Bak, S. (2016). Growth Effects of Leisure Tourism and the Level of Economic Development. *Applied Economics*, *48*(1), 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2015.1073838>
- MinistérioDaSaúde. (2022). *Boletim Epidemiológico de Sífilis* (Technical Report). Secretaria de Vigilância em Saúde.
- MinistérioDoTurismo. (2021). *Anuário Estatístico de Turismo 2020* (Technical Report). CGDI/SGE/SE/MTur. Brasília.
- MinistérioDoTurismo. (2024). Portal de Dados Abertos. Retrieved November 9, 2024, from <https://dados.gov.br/dados/conjuntos-dados/categorizacao>
- Nouchi, A., Caby, F., Palich, R., Monsel, G., & Caumes, A. E. (2019). Travel-associated STI amongst HIV and non-HIV infected travellers. *Journal of Travel Medicine*, *26*(8), taz090.
- Nzivo, M. M., Lwembe, R. M., Odari, E. O., Kang’ethe, J. M., & Budambula, N. L. M. (2019). Prevalence and Risk Factors of Human Herpes Virus Type 8 (HHV-8), Human Immunodeficiency Virus-1 (HIV-1), and Syphilis among Female Sex Workers in Malindi, Kenya. *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Infectious Diseases*, *2019*, 5345161.
- Peeling, R. W., Mabey, D., Chen, X.-S., & Garcia, P. J. (2023). Syphilis. *The Lancet*, *402*(10398), 336–346.
- Pérez-Molina, J. A., Martínez-Perez, A., Serre, N., Treviño, B., Ruiz-Giardín, J. M., Torrús, D., Goikoetxea, J., Echevarría, E. M., Malmierca, E., Rojo, G., Calabuig, E., Gutierrez, B., Norman, F., & Lopez-Velez, R. (2016). Characteristics of HIV infected individuals traveling abroad. Results from the

- +REDIVI Collaborative Network. *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica*, 34(2), 108–113.
- Person, K. I., Berglund, T., Bergström, J., Tikkanen, R., Thorson, A., & Forsberg, B. (2018). Place and Practice: Sexual Risk Behaviour While Travelling Abroad Among Swedish Men Who Have Sex with Men. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 25, 58–64.
- Quaife, M., Diallo, M., Jaye, A., & Martinez-Alvarez, M. (2023). Partnership Preferences, Economic Drivers, and Health Consequences of Gambian Men's Interactions with Foreign Tourists: A Mixed Methods Study. *PLOS global public health*, 3(2), e0001115.
- Queiroz, R. L. d., & Martins, J. S. B. (2024). Estratégia Low-Code com Aprendizado de Máquina para a área de Saúde: Avaliando a Correlação da Atividade Ocupacional com a Incidência de Câncer no Brasil. *Facit Business and Technology Journal (JNT)*, 52(1), 185–206.
- Raimundo, D. M. d. L., Sousa, G. J. B., da Silva, A. B. P., Almino, R. H. S. C., Prado, N. C. d. C., & da Silva, R. A. R. (2021). Spatial analysis of congenital syphilis in the State of Rio Grande do Norte, between 2008 and 2018. *Revista Da Escola De Enfermagem Da U S P*, 55, e20200578.
- Rogstad, K. E. (2019). Sexually Transmitted Infections and Travel: Current Opinion in Infectious Diseases. *LWW*.
- Salavec, M., Bostik, V., Kapla, J., Plisek, S., Prasil, P., Prymula, R., & Bostik, P. (2014). A repeated syphilis infection imported from Thailand in an HIV positive couple of men-who-have-sex-with-men in Czech Republic. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 12(1), 84–87.
- Schäfer, A. (2020). Sexuell Transmissible Infektionen und Tourismus. *Die Gynäkologie*, 53(2), 105–116.
- Shtern, M., & Tzerpos, V. (2009). Methods for Selecting and Improving Software Clustering Algorithms [ISSN: 1092-8138]. *2009 IEEE 17th International Conference on Program Comprehension*, 248–252.
- Signor, M., Spagnolo, L. M. d. L., Tomberg, J. O., Gobatto, M., & Stofel, N. S. (2018). Distribuição Espacial e Caracterização de Casos de Sífilis Congênita. *Revista de Enfermagem UFPE on line*, 12(2), 398–406.
- Simkhada, P. P., Sharma, A., Teijlingen, E. R. v., & Beanland, R. L. (2016). Factors Influencing Sexual Behaviour Between Tourists and Tourism Employees: A Systematic Review. *Nepal Journal of Epidemiology*, 6(1), 530–38.
- Soares, K. K. S., Prado, T. N. d., Zandonade, E., Moreira-Silva, S. F., & Miranda, A. E. (2020). Análise espacial da sífilis em gestantes e sífilis congênita no estado do Espírito Santo, 2011-2018. *Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde*, 29, e2018193.
- Soriano, V., & Romero, J. D. (2018). Rebound in Sexually Transmitted Infections Following the Success of Antiretrovirals for HIV/AIDS. *AIDS reviews*, 20(4), 187–204.
- Sundbeck, M., Emmelin, A., Mannheimer, L., Mjörner, H., & Agardh, A. (2016). Sexual Risk-Taking During Travel Abroad – a Cross-Sectional Survey Among Youth in Sweden. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 14(3), 233–241.
- Svensson, P., Sundbeck, M., Person, K. I., Stafström, M., Östergren, P.-O., Mannheimer, L., & Agardh, A. (2018). A Meta-Analysis and Systematic Literature Review of Factors Associated with Sexual Risk-Taking During International Travel. *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 24, 65–88.
- Teixeira, I. V., Leite, M. T. d. S., Melo, F. L. d. M., Rocha, É. d. S., Sadok, S., Carrarine, A. S. P. d. C., Santana, M., Rodrigues, C. P., Oliveira, A. M. d. L., Gadelha, K. V., Morais, C. M. d., Kelner, J., & Endo, P. T. (2022, October). Predicting Congenital Syphilis Cases: A Performance Evaluation of Different Machine Learning Models.
- Uddin, S., Khan, A., Hossain, M. E., & Moni, M. A. (2019). Comparing Different Supervised Machine Learning Algorithms for Disease Prediction. *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, 19(1), 281.
- Vivancos, R., Abubakar, I., & Hunter, P. R. (2010). Foreign Travel, Casual Sex, and Sexually Transmitted Infections: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [Publisher: Elsevier]. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 14(10), e842–e851.

- Xu, X., Ge, Z., Chow, E. P. F., Yu, Z., Lee, D., Wu, J., Ong, J. J., Fairley, C. K., & Zhang, L. (2022). A Machine-Learning-Based Risk-Prediction Tool for HIV and Sexually Transmitted Infections Acquisition over the Next 12 Months. *Journal of Clinical Medicine, 11*(7), 1818.
- Xu, X., Yu, Z., Ge, Z., Chow, E. P. F., Bao, Y., Ong, J. J., Li, W., Wu, J., Fairley, C. K., & Zhang, L. (2022). Web-Based Risk Prediction Tool for an Individual's Risk of HIV and Sexually Transmitted Infections Using Machine Learning Algorithms: Development and External Validation Study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research, 24*(8), e37850.
- Yalçinkaya, Ö., Daştan, M., & Karabulut, K. (2018). The Effects of International Tourism Receipts on Economic Growth: Evidence from the First 20 Highest Income Earning Countries from Tourism in the World (1996-2016). *Montenegrin Journal of Economics, 14*, 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.14254/1800-5845/2018.14-3.4>
- Young, S. D., Torrone, E. A., Urata, J., & Aral, S. O. (2018). Using Search Engine Data as a tool to Predict Syphilis. *Epidemiology (Cambridge, Mass.), 29*(4), 574–578.
- Zhao, S., Sun, J., Shimizu, K., & Kadota, K. (2018). Silhouette Scores for Arbitrary Defined Groups in Gene Expression Data and Insights into Differential Expression Results. *Biological Procedures Online, 20*, 5.

APPENDIX

Table VII
SCHEMA OF THE SYPHILIS DATABASE (2010–2019)

Column Name	Description	Data Type	Example
Código	IBGE code of the municipality	Numeric	290010
Nome Município	Name of the municipality	Text	Abaíra
qtd_casos	Absolute number of reported syphilis cases	Integer	2
categoria	Tourism category of the municipality (0 = none; 5 = highest)	Integer (0–5)	2
CEP Inicial	Starting postal code range of the municipality (used for georeferencing)	Numeric	46690000
Habitantes	Estimated total population of the municipality	Integer	9199